

Synthesis, antitubercular and antimicrobial activity of 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-[*p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[*b*]thiophenoylamino)phenyl]-2-cyclohexenones

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6-Carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-[*p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[*b*]thiophenoylamino)phenyl]-2-cyclohexenones (**2a-j**) are obtained from the chalcones (**1a-j**) by Michael addition of ethyl acetoacetate, followed by internal Claisen condensation. The synthesized compounds are evaluated for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activity.

Cyclohexenone derivatives exhibit variety of biological activities¹. Our strategy is based on literature precedents that the combinations of fused bicyclic ring system with pharmacologically active heterocyclic entities in molecular framework, may result in compounds with better drug potential. Keeping in view these findings, we are reporting herein the synthesis of some novel cyclohexenones (**2a-j**).

The starting compounds 1-[*p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[*b*]thiophenoylamino)phenyl]-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (**1a-l**) were synthesized² by the reaction of *p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[*b*]thiophenoylamino)acetophenone with different aldehyde. Micheal addition of **1a-l** with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of K₂CO₃ followed by internal Claisen condensation afforded³ 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-[*p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[*b*]thiophenoylamino)phenyl]-2-cyclohexenones (**2a-l**).

Antitubercular activity was evaluated at 6.25 µg ml⁻¹ concentration against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv in BACTEC 12B medium using the ALAMAR radiometric system. The antimycobacterial activity data were compared with standard drug Rifampin at 0.25 µg ml⁻¹ concentration, which showed 98% inhibition. Compounds **Ig** (74 mm, zone of inhibition), **Ih** (56), **Ii** (97), **Ij** (51), **2a** (63), **2e** (42) showed good activity, while compound **Ii** (97) showed significant activity. Other compounds were moderately active or inactive.

Antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method⁴ against bacteria *Escheriachia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus magaterium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungus *Aspergillus niger* at 40 mg ml⁻¹ concentration using amoxycillin (20–26 mm zone of inhibition), ampicillin (16–28), ciprofloxacin (10–26), erythromycin (20–26) and griseofulvin (25) as standards.

R	R
2a C ₆ H ₅ -	g 3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -
b 3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	h 3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₂ -
c 2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	i 4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -
d 3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	j 2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -
e 4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	k 3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -
f 4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	l 3-OC ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -

Compounds **1e** (20), and **1f** (21) were active against *E. coli*. Compounds **1a** (21), **1d** (20), **2e** (23), **2f** (22) and **2j** (19) were active against *P. aeruginosa* and **1b** (19), **2b** (22) and **2i** (19) were active against *B. magaterium*. Compounds **1a** (23), **1c** (28), **2b** (26) and **2f** (23) exhibited significant activity against *S. aureus*. The compounds **2j** (21), **1a** (22), **1b** (24), **1g** (21) and **1i** (22) displayed maximum activity against *A. niger*.

Experimental

Thin layer chromatography was used to monitor the reactions and check purity of the compounds. M.ps. were determined in open glass capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400 instrument and ^1H NMR spectra on a Bruker AC-300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

1-[p-(3'-Chloro-2'-benzo[b]thiophenylamino)phenyl]-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-ones (1f): An ethanolic solution of *p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[b]thiophenylamino)-acetophenone (3.30 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (1.35 g, 0.01 mol) in presence of catalytic amount of 40% KOH was stirred for 24 h at RT. It was then poured over crushed ice and the product formed was crystallized from ethanol. **1f** (78%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 67.11; H, 3.57; N, 3.12. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClNO}_3\text{S}$ requires : C, 67.09; H, 3.54; N, 3.13%); λ_{max} 3055 (CH=CH, aromatic), 2958 (CH_3 asym.), 1659 (C=O), 730 (C-S-C), 545 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.04 (1H, dd, CH=CH), 8.19 (1H, dd, CH=CH), 7.02–8.04 (12H, m Ar-H); m/z 447.

Similarly other compounds were prepared **1a**, m.p. 224°, **b**, 152°, **c**, 149°, **d**, 158°, **e**, 182°, **f**, 158°, **g**, 169°, **h**, 174°, **i**, 128°, **j**, 176°, **k**, 171° and **l**, 178°; in 58–74% yields.

6-Carboethoxy-5-aryl-3-[p-3'-chloro-2'-benzo[b]thiophenylamino)phenyl]-2-cyclohexenones (2f): A mixture of 1-[*p*-(3'-chloro-2'-benzo[b]thiophenylamino)phenyl]-3-*p*-methoxyphenyl-2-propen-1-one (4.48 g, 0.01 mol) in 50 ml of dry acetone, anhydrous K_2CO_3 (5.42 g, 0.04 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (2.60 g, 0.02 mol) was stirred at RT overnight and was filtered. The solvent from the filtrate on evaporation gave a solid, which was crystallized from ethanol, yield 69%, m.p. 214° (Found : C, 65.45; H, 4.62; N, 2.49. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{26}\text{ClNO}_5\text{S}$ requires : C, 65.48; H, 4.64;

N, 2.50%); IR (KBr) 1735 (C=O, ester), 1668 (C=O, ketone), 756 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 0.96 (3H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 3.02 (1H, dd, J 2.41 Hz, methylene $-\text{CH}_a$), 3.41 (1H, dd, J 4.14 Hz, methylene $-\text{CH}_b$), 3.55 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}_c$), 3.90 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}_d$), 3.84 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 3.96 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 6.56 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $-\text{CH}_d$), 6.88–8.17 (12H, m, Ar-H); m/z 560.

Similarly other compounds **2a**, m.p. 174°, **b**, 142°, **c**, 153°, **d** 158°, **e**, 169°, **f**, 214°, **g**, 50°, **h**, 198°, **i**, 205°, **j**, 198°, **k**, 152° and **l**, 138°; in 61–71% yields.

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